

Integration of Aesthetics and Education in Digital Games: A Visual Communication Design Perspective Based on the Tri Hita Karana Philosophy

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Abstract

The rapid development of digital technology has positioned digital games as powerful interactive media that integrate fun, education, and visual communication. This study explores the integration of aesthetics and education in the design of a *Tri Hita Karana*-based educational game, adopting a practice-based research approach within the framework of Design Thinking. The game was developed as a 2D side-scrolling prototype featuring three main areas *palemahan* (nature), *pawongan* (human relations), and *parahyangan* (spirituality) with contextual missions such as waste segregation, river and coastal clean-ups, and symbolic interactions with Balinese cultural icons. Semiotic elements including icons, indexes, and symbols were employed to translate abstract ecological concepts into messages accessible to children. User testing was conducted with 30 children aged 8–12 years in Desa Adat Cangu, Bali, using flow experience and environmental awareness questionnaires, as well as direct observation. Results showed that 80% of participants reported high focus, 76% found the challenges balanced with their skills, and 83% fully enjoyed the game, indicating optimal flow conditions. Moreover, 70% of children could recall waste categories, 65% were motivated to dispose of waste properly, and 60% expressed willingness to encourage peers, reflecting cognitive, affective, and social impacts. The study contributes theoretically by enriching discourses on visual communication design in game-based learning, practically by offering a design model rooted in local wisdom, and culturally by demonstrating the relevance of *Tri Hita Karana* values in interactive digital media. Limitations include the small sample size and prototype scope, suggesting future research with larger trials and advanced features such as multiplayer or augmented reality.

Keywords: *Visual Communication Design, Educational Game, Tri Hita Karana, Flow Experience, Environmental Awareness.*

Suggested citation: Saskara, I.P.A., Swandi, I.W., Artadi, I.M.P., & Dewi, A.K. (2025). Integration of Aesthetics and Education in Digital Games: A Visual Communication Design Perspective Based on the Tri Hita Karana Philosophy. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(6), 3-13. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(6).01

Introduction

The rapid development of digital technology has significantly transformed the way humans communicate, learn, and interact with cultural values. Digital games, which were once considered merely entertainment, have now become powerful interactive media that integrate elements of fun, education, and visual communication (Sutopo, 2020). In the field of education, this transformation is encapsulated in the concept of game-based learning, where children's learning processes are facilitated through play activities. Such an approach has been proven to enhance attention, motivation, and knowledge retention (Colliver & Veraksa, 2019). When aligned with the principles of visual communication design (VCD), through

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visual language, icons, colors, symbols, and interactivity, games act as moving visual messages that simultaneously touch the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains (Kwastek, 2015).

In Indonesia, environmental issues have become an urgent challenge. According to data from the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), Bali produced 915.5 thousand tons of waste in 2021, which increased by 12.22% to around 1.02 million tons in 2022, making Bali the eighth largest waste-producing province in Indonesia (Annur, 2023). Moreover, Bali has recently been hit by floods, one of the causes of which was the accumulation of waste. In Desa Adat Canggu, one of Bali's most popular tourist destinations, rapid tourism growth has been accompanied by an increase in waste pollution, especially in rivers and coastal areas (KompasTV, 2023). Field observations conducted in June 2024 revealed severe waste accumulation in waterways and on beaches (see Figure 1) (Saskara, 2024). This condition not only degrades environmental quality but also threatens public health and Bali's tourism image (Xu et al., 2022)

Figure 1. Waste in Several Areas of Desa Adat Canggu
Source: Saskara's Documentation, 2024

Tri Hita Karana (THK), a Balinese philosophy that emphasizes harmony between humans and God (*parahyangan*), humans and fellow humans (*pawongan*), and humans and the natural environment (*palemahan*), provides a culturally rooted framework for addressing ecological issues (Peters & Wardana, 2013; Peterson, 2017). Although THK has been widely applied in fields such as tourism, architecture, and education, its integration into digital game design remains underexplored. Embedding THK into digital educational media, particularly games, allows environmental messages to be communicated not only verbally but also visually, symbolically, and interactively in ways that resonate with children (Diantari & Gede Agung, 2021; Lestiawati et al., 2023; Windawati & Koeswanti, 2021)

From a visual communication design perspective, creating an educational game based on THK involves more than programming mechanics; it requires the design of a visual language system that is communicative, aesthetic, and symbolic. Elements such as color palettes that reference natural balance, icons representing waste categorization, cultural symbols such as *pelinggih* (shrines) and *gapura* (gates), as well as interactive layouts specifically tailored for children, must be carefully crafted (Kwastek, 2015). In addition, maintaining children's engagement is essential, which can be achieved through the application of flow theory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). A visual design that balances challenge and skill ensures that players remain motivated and engaged (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Flow Experience Scheme in the Educational Game (Csikszentmihalyi)

Although research on educational games in Indonesia is growing (Faizal et al., 2021; Kusumandari, 2019; Nirwana, 2021), a significant gap remains. Most studies focus solely on cognitive aspects, such as mastery of mathematical concepts or the introduction of science, without integrating local wisdom frameworks such as *Tri Hita Karana* (THK) into interactive media for children. Furthermore, few studies explicitly link visual semiotics and interaction aesthetics in visual communication design (VCD) with measurable indicators, such as children’s level of engagement and their ecological understanding. The following Table 1 presents a comparison of several previous studies:

Table 1. Comparison of Studies on Educational Games in Indonesia

Researcher & Year	Research Focus	Method/Media	Key Findings	Limitations (Gap)
Kusumandari (2019)	Educational game for introducing basic mathematics	Android-based game	Children were more enthusiastic about learning through games; improved understanding of basic mathematical concepts.	Did not integrate local cultural values; focus limited only to cognitive material.
Nirwana (2021)	Educational game for animal introduction	2D interactive multimedia	Interactive visuals helped children recognize animal species and their habitats.	Did not address aspects of local wisdom and character values; aesthetics remained generic.
Faizal et al. (2021)	Science-based environmental educational game	Unity-based interactive game	Symbolic visuals enhanced children’s understanding of waste recycling.	Environmental messages were conveyed scientifically without reinforcement of local cultural values.

From the table, it can be seen that the majority of educational games in Indonesia still emphasize the delivery of information in cognitive or scientific terms. Few studies have made serious efforts to integrate local wisdom in visual, symbolic, or philosophical forms. This gap provides the space for innovation in

the present study, namely the development of an educational game based on *Tri Hita Karana* that simultaneously demonstrates how visual communication design (VCD) can serve as a bridge between local cultural values and environmental education in an interactive digital format.

In line with this, the study has three main objectives:

1. To describe the design of visual language and interaction in a *Tri Hita Karana*-based digital game, encompassing elements of iconography, color, cultural symbols, and game mechanics as a medium for children's environmental education.
2. To analyze how visual semiotics and interaction aesthetics through icons, indexes, symbols, and visual-auditory feedback can strengthen ecological messages within the context of visual communication design.
3. To present the results of user testing with children aged 8–12 years to validate the effectiveness of applying visual communication design principles in supporting engagement (*flow experience*) and enhancing environmental awareness.

Literature Review

Visual Communication Design (VCD) and Interactive Media

Visual Communication Design (VCD) is a discipline focused on how messages are conveyed through visual elements such as typography, color, icons, symbols, layout, and illustration. The main goal of VCD is to create communication that is effective, persuasive, and aesthetic (Rustan, 2010). In the context of interactive media, VCD is not only concerned with visual aspects but also organizes user experience, ensuring that interactions between users and media are communicative and meaningful (Kwastek, 2015).

Semiotics in VCD provides an important framework for understanding the role of visual signs. Peirce in (I. S. Rahayu, 2021) categorized signs into icons, indexes, and symbols. In educational games, an icon could be a trash bin image representing disposal, an index could be an arrow indicating the player's direction of movement, while a symbol could be a Balinese carving motif referring to certain spiritual values. Thus, semiotics helps game designers formulate a visual language capable of conveying messages both directly and symbolically.

Interaction aesthetics is also a key pillar in contemporary VCD. According to Silvennoinen, (2021) aesthetics in design extends beyond visualization to include user experience during interaction. In digital games, interaction aesthetics are reflected in how players respond to colors, shapes, animations, and audio-visual feedback when performing certain actions. The more harmonious the relationship between visual display and user response, the higher the level of engagement created.

Game-Based Learning and Flow Experience

Game-based learning is a learning method that uses game mechanics to deliver educational content. According to Warren & Jones, (2017), games hold great potential as learning media because they provide simulations, challenges, and feedback that keep learners actively engaged. The principle of learning through play has been proven to enhance cognitive abilities while motivating children to learn without feeling burdened (Colliver & Veraksa, 2019).

The concept of flow, introduced by Csikszentmihalyi in (Tse et al., 2022) is also relevant in this context. Flow is a psychological state in which a person is fully immersed in an activity, experiencing a balance between skills and challenges. In educational games, this balance is realized through level design, game difficulty, and visualizations that stimulate curiosity without causing frustration. The Flow Experience scheme used in this study (see Figure 2) emphasizes the importance of VCD in maintaining children's gameplay experience so they do not fall into boredom or anxiety.

Visual Aesthetics in Educational Games

Visual aesthetics serve as elements that enhance both the appeal and clarity of messages in educational games. According to Wiratno & Callula, (2024), digital aesthetics represent the convergence of art, design, and technology. In environmentally themed games, aesthetics can be designed by emphasizing green, blue, and brown colors associated with nature, or by incorporating cultural motifs related to environmental harmony.

Research by Faizal et al., (2021) shows that children more easily understand environmental messages when conveyed through symbolic and interactive visuals compared to verbal text. This aligns with the VCD approach that emphasizes visual literacy as a medium of communication. In a *Tri Hita Karana*-based game, visual aesthetics not only enhance children's engagement but also internalize Balinese cultural values through representations of local symbols such as *pelelinggih* (shrines), *gapura* (gates), or distinctive Balinese flora and fauna ornaments.

The Philosophy of Tri Hita Karana (THK) in the Context of Education

The philosophy of *Tri Hita Karana* is a Balinese worldview that emphasizes harmony in three dimensions: *parahyangan* (human–God relationship), *pawongan* (human–human relationship), and *palemahan* (human–nature relationship). This concept is not only religious but also practical in daily life, including in environmental management (Peters & Wardana, 2013).

In the context of education, THK can serve as a foundation for instilling environmental values from an early age. Lestiawati et al., (2023) demonstrated that the integration of local wisdom into learning media enhances children's understanding of ecological issues while simultaneously building their cultural identity. By embedding THK into digital games, children not only learn about waste segregation but also realize that caring for the environment is part of their spirituality and social life.

Methodology

Research Approach

This study employs a practice-based research approach, a research method that focuses on creative practice as the core of the research process (Vear et al., 2021). In this context, the *Tri Hita Karana*-based digital game is positioned as a visual communication design work that is both created and used as an object of scholarly reflection.

In addition, the Design Thinking framework is applied to guide the stages of creation, which include: *empathize*, *define*, *ideate*, *prototype*, *testing*, and *maintenance* (see Figure 3). Each stage produces visual, conceptual, and functional outputs that serve as the foundation for the subsequent stage of development.

Figure 3. Edugame Thinking Process

Research Location and Subjects

This research was conducted in Desa Adat Canggu, North Kuta District, Badung Regency, Bali. The location was selected because it represents a dynamic tourism area with significant environmental impacts, particularly in terms of waste generation. Field observations indicated that most children aged 8–12 years in the village already own personal smartphones, making digital games a highly relevant medium in their daily lives. In addition, the presence of local environmental communities and organizations, such as Sungai Watch and EcoBali, provides contextual partners that reinforce the relevance of environmental conservation issues. The trial subjects in this study were children aged 8–12 years, who represented the target users of the game. A total of 30 children participated in the initial trial, selected through purposive sampling.

Research Procedure

The research procedure followed the stages of the Design Thinking framework. In the empathize stage, environmental observations were conducted in Desa Adat Canggu to understand the waste problem, complemented by interviews with community leaders, environmental activists (Sungai Watch), and children regarding their gaming habits and their awareness of environmental issues.

In the define stage, the main problem was formulated as the low level of children's awareness regarding waste segregation. The study then determined the objective of integrating the *Tri Hita Karana* philosophy into interactive educational media, while also specifying the technical requirements: an Android-based platform, 2D graphics, a child-friendly interface, and the integration of AI-powered waste detection (YOLO v11).

The ideate stage focused on designing the visual concepts, which included icons, colors, and Balinese motifs informed by a study of visual semiotics. At this stage, the game mechanics were also determined, consisting of waste collection, organic and inorganic segregation, point accumulation, and the integration of flow experience. Preliminary sketches of characters, environments, and the game interface were also developed.

Subsequently, in the prototype stage, the research team developed a functional prototype using Unity 2D and integrated a camera-based waste detection system powered by the YOLO v11 AI model. The prototype included three main levels representing the domains of *palemahan* (environment), *pawongan* (community), and *parahyangan* (spirituality).

During the testing stage, trials were conducted with 30 children aged 8–12 years. Three instruments were used: (1) a Flow Experience questionnaire based on Csikszentmihalyi's theory (Tse et al., 2022), (2) a questionnaire measuring environmental knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors, and (3) direct observation of children's responses while playing the game.

Finally, the maintenance stage involved improving the visuals, interface, and mechanics of the game based on trial results. At this stage, dissemination strategies were also prepared, including distribution through the Google Play Store, the publication of gameplay videos on YouTube, and the implementation of school-based workshops to introduce the game to a broader audience.

Results and Discussion

Game Development Results

The educational game based on *Tri Hita Karana* developed in this study is a 2D side-scrolling game with a simple, child-friendly interface. On the start screen (main menu), players are presented with navigation options such as *Play*, *Scan*, *Shop*, and *Exit* (see Figure 4). This design emphasizes gameplay flexibility, where the *Scan* feature connects players to a camera-based waste detection system, while the *Shop* feature serves as an additional educational space through a reward mechanism.

Figure 4. Game Development Results

Next, players can choose from three main areas that represent the philosophy of *Tri Hita Karana*: Palemahan (nature), Pawongan (human relations), and Parahyangan (spirituality). Each area is designed with contextual missions: maintaining the cleanliness of rivers and beaches, collaborating with NPCs to manage waste, and honoring nature through Balinese religious symbols.

From a visual perspective, the game adopts a visual communication design (VCD) approach using a flat design style to ensure clarity and accessibility for children. Natural colors such as green, blue, and brown were selected to reinforce the impression of nature. In addition, local cultural symbols such as *gapura* (traditional gates) and *pelinggih* (shrines) are displayed within the game areas (see Figure 4, lower right). These visual elements are not merely decorative ornaments but carry semiotic meaning:

1. Icons: trash bins labeled organic–inorganic, images of plastic bottles, and leaves that help children understand waste classification.
2. Indexes: the visual transformation of a river from murky to clear after a cleaning mission, serving as a sign of ecological achievement.
3. Symbols: the presence of *gapura* and *pelinggih* emphasizes the spiritual relationship with nature and the religious dimension of the *Tri Hita Karana* philosophy.

Integration of Aesthetics and Education

The design results show that the integration of aesthetics and education was achieved through several aspects:

1. Visual Aesthetics

The interface design and game elements employ natural colors, child-friendly characters, and simple iconography. This supports the VCD principle that visuals should be communicative as well as enjoyable (S. Rahayu et al., 2021)

2. Gameplay

The game missions include segregating organic–inorganic waste (see Figure 4, lower right), crossing rivers to clean up areas (see Figure 4, lower left), and other educational activities such as tree planting. In this way, children learn environmental concepts through activities that resemble everyday play rather than formal learning instructions.

3. Visual Auditory Feedback

Each success by the player for instance, when correctly sorting waste is rewarded with a green light effect and a soft gamelan sound. This combination functions as *positive reinforcement* (Skinner, 1984) enhancing emotional engagement while reinforcing children's memory of environmental messages.

This integration of aesthetics and education affirms that games do not merely serve as entertainment but also as persuasive, interactive, and meaningful learning media when designed from a visual communication design perspective.

Playing Experience and Flow

Children's gameplay experiences show that the *Hita Karana* game successfully fosters the state of *flow* as described by Csikszentmihalyi (Tse et al., 2022). Flow is a psychological condition in which players are fully immersed in an activity, experiencing a balance between challenge and skill.

In this game, flow indicators are clearly embedded in the interface features: life, score, health, and timer (see Figure 4). These elements provide players with direct feedback about their achievements and limitations. For example, losing "life" when failing to cross the river or gaining "score" when successfully sorting waste motivates children to keep trying. The interface, although simple, remains responsive and supports the creation of an immersive experience suited to children's abilities.

The trial with 30 children (aged 8–12) demonstrated that most players experienced optimal flow conditions. Questionnaire results show that:

1. 80% of children felt fully focused while playing, indicating high cognitive engagement.
2. 76% considered the challenges appropriate to their abilities, demonstrating that the game mechanics align with the principle of balancing challenge and skill.
3. 83% fully enjoyed the game, reflecting positive emotional experiences that support learning through enjoyment.

Thus, it can be concluded that the simple user interface (UI), visual–auditory feedback system, and structured gameplay mechanics successfully created flow conditions that enhance environmental learning through digital media.

Children's Responses to Environmental Messages

Beyond the flow experience, this study also evaluated how effectively the *Hita Karana* game conveyed environmental messages. Children's responses after playing showed a significant increase in ecological awareness.

The questionnaire results revealed (see Figure 5):

1. 70% of children were able to recall the categories of waste (organic and inorganic) after playing. This indicates that the iconography and visualizations of organic–inorganic trash bins successfully functioned as semiotic media that were easily understood.
2. 65% of children reported being motivated to dispose of waste properly. The gameplay mechanics waste collection, river crossing, and visual–auditory feedback proved effective in encouraging children to internalize ecological behavior.
3. 60% expressed willingness to encourage their peers to care for the environment. This highlights the emergence of a social dimension in environmental messaging, consistent with the concept of *pawongan* in *Tri Hita Karana*, which emphasizes harmony among humans.

Figure 5. Children's Responses to Environmental Messages

From these data, it is evident that the integration of ecological messages through visual semiotics, educational gameplay, and interaction aesthetics can influence the cognitive domain (knowledge of waste types), the affective domain (motivation to dispose of waste properly), and the social domain (initiative to encourage peers). Thus, the *Hita Karana* game not only enhances children's understanding but also fosters attitudes and behavioral intentions aligned with the principles of environmental conservation.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the integration of aesthetics and education in a *Tri Hita Karana*-based digital game can be effectively realized through visual communication design. The results of the design process and trials with children in Desa Adat Canggu reveal that simple icons, natural colors, and Balinese cultural symbols functioned as semiotic elements that successfully translated abstract ecological concepts into messages easily understood by children. The combination of gameplay mechanics and interaction aesthetics, supported by visual and auditory feedback as positive reinforcement, significantly enhanced children's motivation and engagement, while the balance of challenges and skills fostered an optimal flow experience as theorized by Csikszentmihalyi (Tse et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the children's responses indicated not only improved knowledge of waste types but also stronger motivation to act environmentally responsibly and even to encourage peers, reflecting the internalization of ecological and cultural values. These findings highlight three main contributions: theoretically, enriching the discourse on the role of visual communication design in game-based learning within the Balinese context; practically, offering a design model for developing educational games rooted in local wisdom; and culturally, affirming that the values of *Tri Hita Karana* can be transformed into digital interactive media that remain relevant in the era of globalization.

Nonetheless, this study has limitations, particularly its small-scale trial involving only 30 children and its prototype stage. Future research should involve a larger sample, integrate advanced features such as multiplayer or augmented reality, and explore children's psychological dimensions over the long term. Overall, this study confirms that visual communication design is not merely about producing visual aesthetics but also about serving as a strategic medium to deliver educational messages and preserve local cultural values through interactive digital media.

Acknowledgment

The author would like to express sincere gratitude to the Indonesian Institute of the Arts (ISI) Bali, particularly the lecturers and the editorial team of the affiliated journal, for providing an invaluable academic platform for publication. Deep appreciation is also conveyed to the supervisors and examiners, whose guidance, feedback, and constructive advice have been essential in completing this research and manuscript.

The author is also thankful to the community of Desa Adat Canggü, especially the children who enthusiastically participated in the trials, as well as environmental organizations such as Sungai Watch and EcoBali for their contextual support and collaboration. Finally, heartfelt appreciation goes to the author's family and friends for their prayers, motivation, and unwavering support throughout the course of this research.

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